

Kizimkazi Dimbani Mosque Inscription

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Entry tags: Quranic Inscription, Dedicatory Inscription, Religious Group, Abrahamic, African Religions, Islam, Ritual inscriptions, Arabic, Islamic Traditions, Ritual text, Swahili Religion, Sunni, Semitic, Text, Arabian, Afro-Asiatic, Central Semitic, Transnational Islam, West Semitic, Language, Arabian Peninsula Arabic, Standard Arabic, African Religion, Islam in Africa, Swahili Islam, Islam

The mosque at Kizimkazi Dimbani, located on the southern coast of the island of Unguja (Zanzibar) is important because it boasts an inscription that dates to 1107CE and is one of the earliest extant mosques on the Swahili coast. The inscription is located on the northern wall of the mosque and runs into the mihrab. It reads as follows: "This is what has ordered the high and very great Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of al Hasan, son of Muhammad . . .—may Allah grant him long life and destroy his enemies—about building this mosque on a Sunday of the month Dhu-lqa'da in the year five hundred (A.D. 1107)." To the right of the mihrab is a quote from the Quran (ch. ix, 18). The alcove of the mihrab is inscribed with verses 80-82 of ch. xvii of the Quran. Two rosettes are placed above the mihrab. The rosette on the right contains verse 24 of ch. xiii of the Quran, while the rosette on the left has not been fully deciphered. A later inscription (placed atop an erased portion of the original inscription) says that the mosque was rebuilt in 1770 CE. This inscription is important not only because it is evidence for the early presence of Islam on Zanzibar (1107CE), but also because it is written in the floriate and plaited Kufic script. This suggests that a foreign craftsman/calligrapher was involved in the placing of this dedicatory inscription in the mosque. The construction of the mosque itself has been linked to immigrant Near Eastern populations rather than as a product of local construction. However, like at the Swahili "stone towns", the mosque is built of limestone and plastered over with burnt limestone plaster. The entry on the Kizimkazi Mosque provides information on the mosque itself.

Date Range: 1107 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Kizimkazi Dimbani, Unguja Island

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Tanzania, Unguja

The village of Kizimkazi Dimbani, located on the southern coast of Unguja (Zanzibar) Island

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Flury, S. (1922). The Kufic Inscription of Kizimkazi Mosque, Zanzibar, AD 1107. *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 21, 257-264.
- Source 2: Chami, M. F. (2017). Management of Religious Heritage in Tanzania: A Case Study of Kizimkazi Mosque on Zanzibar Island. *The Annual Review of Islam*, 14, 67-76.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: None
- Source 1 Description: None
- Source 2 URL: None
- Source 2 Description: None
- Source 3 URL: None
- Source 3 Description: None

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: None
- Source 1 Description: None
- Source 2 URL: None
- Source 2 Description: None
- Source 3 URL: None
- Source 3 Description: None

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

- Chisel
- Knife
- Other [specify]: Carving tool

Notes: The inscription was carved into the limestone plaster (possibly when wet) on the north wall of the Kizimkazi mosque.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Stone

Notes: The inscription is located in the plaster coating of the limestone wall of the Kizimkazi mosque.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Overwritten

Notes: The original inscription has been overwritten by a later inscription.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Overwritten

Notes: The original inscription has been overwritten by a later inscription.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb
– No

Cemetery
– No

Temple
– No

Shrine
– No

Altar
– No

Devotional marker
– No

Cenotaph
– No

Church
– No

↳ Mosque

– Yes

Notes: The inscription(s) are located on the north wall (with the mihrab, thus facing Mecca) of the Kizimkazi Mosque.

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– Yes

Notes: The inscription(s) are located on the north wall (with the mihrab, thus facing Mecca) of the Kizimkazi Mosque. The Kizimkazi Mosque at the time of its construction would have been a monumental structure.

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– Yes

Notes: The inscription(s) are located on the north wall (with the mihrab, thus facing Mecca) of the Kizimkazi Mosque. While small, the Kizimkazi Mosque would have served as the gathering point for about 100 people.

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– No

↳ Specify

– Specify: The inscription(s) are located on the north wall (with the mihrab, thus facing Mecca) of the Kizimkazi Mosque.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Notes: In accordance with standard Islamic practice, the mosque is unadorned except for the calligraphy of the inscription.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Yes

↳ Alpha-numeric symbolism?

– No

↳ Use of geometric/abstract designs?

– Yes

Notes: The inscription is an example of floriate/plaited Kufic, meaning that it is meant to look ornamented and geometrical.

↳ Floral or other natural imagery?

– Yes

Notes: The inscription makes use of floriate/plaited Kufic, and it meant to evoke images of foliage and flowers in the mind of the viewer.

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– I don't know

Notes: The construction of the mosque seems to have been funded by an individual. According to the inscription: "This is what has ordered the high and very great Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of al-Hasan, son of Muhammad . . .—may Allah grant him long life and destroy his enemies—about building this mosque on a Sunday of the month Dhu-lqa'da in the year five hundred (A.D. 1107)." This person could be a representative of a polity, but the construction of this mosque could have also been an act of personal piety. The repair of the mosque of the 1770 could have been the action of a polity or

a pious individual.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: There are Quranic verses located in the mosque in addition to the dedicatory inscription.

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Yes

Notes: The Quran is often recited

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– Yes

Notes: The Quran was revealed to the Prophet Mohammed through the angel Gabriel.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– Yes

Notes: The Quran was revealed to the Prophet Mohammed through the angel Gabriel.

↳ Inspired by high god?

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– No

Notes: The Quran is considered fixed and unalterable.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– Yes

Notes: Ulama are generally tasked with interpreting the Quran, but it must be noted that the syncretic and heterodox nature of East African Islam makes it entirely possible that others took a leading role in the interpretation of the Quran.

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions?

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by official sanctioned figures?

– No

↳ Are there common disagreements? (such as two or more different schools of interpretation?)

– Yes

↳ Are there methods of permanently tabling or resolving debates amongst groups of interpreters?

– I don't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– I don't know

Notes: Yes and no. There are those trained in the study and dissemination of the Quran, but Islam has also spread through the agency of charismatic preachers and merchants.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– Yes

Notes: The Quran is written in Classical Arabic.

↳ Considered endogenous by the group itself?

– Yes

Notes: Arabic was the language of the Prophet Muhammad, and of the original converts to Islam.

↳ Considered exogenous by the group itself?

– No

↳ Blended languages/creolizations/specific dialects?

– Yes

↳ Possess its own distinct written language?

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals?

– No

↳ If known: which authority (authorities) describe(s) the language as sacred?

[Select all that apply]

– Prophet

– Institutions

↳ Are non-religious institutions involved with the support of teaching religious language(s) for this text?

– Yes

↳ Are non-religious written languages used by the group's adherents to support religious study of text?

– Yes

↳ Are oral traditions used to support the religious study of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Hadiths or sayings of the Prophet are important in Quranic interpretation.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: All visitors to the mosque can be considered to be the intended audience of the inscription. The number of people who have passed through this mosque since its construction in 1107 must number in the thousands.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

Notes: Proselytizing is not mandated according to this inscription, but it is an important part of Islam theology detailed in other texts.

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

Notes: Proselytizing is not mandated according to this inscription, but it is an important part of Islam theology detailed in other texts.

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

Notes: Proselytizing is not mandated according to this inscription, but it is an important part of Islam theology detailed in other texts.

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force?

– Yes

Notes: Physical coercion can play a role in proselytizing. However, proselytizing is not mandated according to this inscription, but it is an important part of Islam theology detailed in other texts.

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions?

– Yes

Notes: A special tax known as the jizya was usually levied on non-Muslims by Muslim regimes. However, proselytizing is not mandated according to this inscription, but it is

an important part of Islam theology detailed in other texts.

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– Yes

Notes: It is directed against non-Muslims. Proselytizing is not mandated according to this inscription, but it is an important part of Islam theology detailed in other texts.

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

Notes: Proselytizing is not mandated according to this inscription, but it is an important part of Islam theology detailed in other texts.

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Notes: Proselytizing is not mandated according to this inscription, but it is an important part of Islam theology detailed in other texts.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: There have been multiple reformist movements in Islam over the years.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– I don't know

Notes: The inscription itself was part of the construction of a sacred place, so it may have served ritual function in that capacity. The fact that Quranic verses are part of the inscription make its ritual character more distinct. However, whether this inscription was recited/read in ritual practice at the mosque or whether its ritual character was limited to the construction of the mosque remains unknown.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Notes: The inscription is located on the north wall of the mosque with the mihrab. it was meant for all to read.

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

Notes: The inscription is located on the north wall of the mosque with the mihrab. it was meant for all to read.

↳ Can it be touched?

– Yes

Notes: It can be touched, but one should not because it can be easily damaged.

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– I don't know

Notes: Touching the inscription could have had ritual importance in the past, given the unique and syncretic nature of East African Islam. However, this inscription is not touched as part of ritual practice in the present.

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Yes

Notes: The inclusion of Quranic verses in the inscription could have protective functions.

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– I don't know

Notes: The inclusion of Quranic verses in the inscription could have healing functions. However, the inscription does not have any healing functions at present.

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– I don't know

Notes: The inclusion of Quranic verses in the inscription could have cleansing functions in the past. However, the inscription does not have any cleansing functions at present.

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– I don't know

Notes: The inclusion of Quranic verses in the inscription could have served as a form of expiation in the past, especially during its construction. However, the inscription does not have any expiatory functions at present.

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– I don't know

Notes: The text could have served as an incantation in the past, given the unique nature of East African Islam, especially at the time when the mosque was constructed and the inscription made. However, at present, the text does not serve as an incantation.

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: A part of the inscription was erased and another later inscription added on top of it.

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Specify: Removing/defacing an inscription in Islam is generally frowned upon. However, at this mosque, a part of the inscription was erased and a later inscription added.

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Notes: In accordance with the strictures in Islam against art, no art accompanies the inscription.

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: The dedicatory portion of the inscription seems fairly unique. Further, the sections of the Quran quoted are assumed to have remained fairly stable over time.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The dedicatory portion of the inscription seems fairly unique. The Quranic portions of the inscription are part of the Quran.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: It is a dedicatory inscription.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– I don't know

Notes: The inscription is dedicatory with quoted sections of the Quran.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: It is a dedicatory inscription with quotations from the Quran.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: It is a dedicatory inscription with quotations from the Quran.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription mentions the dedication of the Kizimkazi mosque by a single individual. To quote, "This is what has ordered the high and very great Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad . . .—may Allah grant him long life and destroy his enemies—about building this mosque on a Sunday of the month Dhu-lqa'da in the year five hundred (A.D. 1107)."

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: The inscription is dedicatory with quotations from the Quran.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: The inscription is dedicatory with quotations from the Quran.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription is dedicatory with quotations from the Quran.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Notes: The inscription is dedicatory with quotations from the Quran. But other texts in Islam mention a belief in an afterlife.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The dedicatory text and the Quranic quotations mention Allah, the high god of Islam.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– I don't know

Notes: Allah is often described in anthropomorphic terms and has human-like qualities, but Muslims are prevented from creating or possessing any image of Allah.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– I don't know

Notes: Allah could be considered a sky deity according to some traditions.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Notes: Allah is unquestionably good.

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Beneficent, merciful, eternal, most sacred, embodiment of peace, infuser of faith, preserver of safety, might, omnipotent, dominant, creator, evolver, flawless, shaper, great forgiver, all-prevailing, supreme bestower, total provider, supreme solver, omniscient, the elevating one, honor-bestower, abaser, all-hearer, impartial judge, embodiment of justice, knower of subtleties, clement, magnificent, sublime, great, guardian, sustainer, reckoner, majestic, bountiful, watchful, responsive, omnipresent, wise, loving, glorious, infuser of life, all-observing, embodiment of truth, universal trustee, strong, firm, protective, singly laudable, the one to whom the count of all things are known, originator, restorer, maintainer of life, inflictor of death, self-subsisting, perceptive, all-noble, sole god, all-authoritative, expediter, delayer, first, perceptible, imperceptible, exalted, merciful, retaliator, pardoner, benign, sovereign, majestic, honorable, just, gatherer of creation, self-sufficient, distressor, bestower of sufficiency, preventer, bestower of benefits, prime light, provider of guidance, unique, ever-surviving, eternal inheritor, guide to path of rectitude, extensively enduring

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Notes: Islam is monotheistic.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Beneficent, merciful, eternal, most sacred, embodiment of peace, infuser of faith, preserver of safety, might, omnipotent, dominant, creator, evolver, flawless, shaper, great forgiver, all-prevailing, supreme bestower, total provider, supreme solver, omniscient, the elevating one, honor-bestower, abaser, all-hearer, impartial judge, embodiment of justice, knower of subtleties, clement, magnificent, sublime, great, guardian, sustainer, reckoner, majestic, bountiful, watchful, responsive, omnipresent, wise, loving, glorious, infuser of life, all-observing, embodiment of truth, universal trustee, strong, firm, protective, singly laudable, the one to whom the count of all things are known, originator, restorer, maintainer of life, inflictor of death, self-subsisting, perceptive, all-noble, sole god, all-authoritative, expediter, delayer, first, perceptible, imperceptible, exalted, merciful, retaliator, pardoner, benign, sovereign, majestic, honorable, just, gatherer of creation, self-sufficient, distressor, bestower of sufficiency, preventer, bestower of benefits, prime light, provider of guidance, unique, ever-surviving, eternal inheritor, guide to path of rectitude, extensively enduring

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: Allah communicates with humans through inspiration and through prophets.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– I don't know

Notes: It would depend on how the builder of the mosque would have considered his relationship with Allah. This is entirely possible in the syncretized form of Islam that characterized the pre-colonial East African coast.

↳ In dreams

– I don't know

Notes: It would depend on how the builder of the mosque would have considered his relationship with Allah. This is entirely possible in the syncretized form of Islam that characterized the pre-colonial East African coast.

↳ In trance possession

– I don't know

Notes: It would depend on how the builder of the mosque would have considered his relationship with Allah. This is entirely possible in the syncretized form of Islam that characterized the pre-colonial East African coast. Trance possession was common in East African religious practice (especially in Zanzibar) in the precolonial and early colonial periods.

↳ Through divination practices

– I don't know

Notes: It would depend on how the builder of the mosque would have considered his relationship with Allah. This is entirely possible in the syncretized form of Islam that characterized the pre-colonial East African coast. Divination is an important aspect of religious practice in East Africa today.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– I don't know

Notes: It would depend on how the builder of the mosque would have considered his relationship with Allah. This is entirely possible in the syncretized form of Islam that characterized the pre-colonial East African coast, as is communication with Allah personally or through charismatic preachers.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: Through Quran, inspiration, and Prophets.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– I don't know

Notes: Not necessarily, but it could be that recitation of the Quranic excerpts included in the inscription could have been a way to communicate with the divine. But this is conjecture.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– I don't know

Notes: It would depend on how the builder of the mosque would have considered his relationship with Allah. This is entirely possible in the syncretized form of Islam that characterized the pre-colonial East African coast.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– I don't know

Notes: It would depend on how the builder of the mosque would have considered his relationship with Allah. This is entirely possible in the syncretized form of Islam that characterized the pre-colonial East African coast.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Allah is omniscient

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Notes: But Allah communicates with the living through the Quran, through inspiration, and through the Prophets.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Beneficent, merciful, eternal, most sacred, embodiment of peace, infuser of faith, preserver of safety, might, omnipotent, dominant, creator, evolver, flawless, shaper, great forgiver, all-prevailing, supreme bestower, total provider, supreme solver, omniscient, the elevating one, honor-bestower, abaser, all-hearer, impartial judge, embodiment of justice, knower of subtleties, clement, magnificent, sublime, great, guardian, sustainer, reckoner, majestic, bountiful, watchful, responsive, omnipresent, wise, loving, glorious, infuser of life, all-observing, embodiment of truth, universal trustee, strong, firm, protective, singly laudable, the one to whom the count of all things are known, originator, restorer, maintainer of life, inflictor of death, self-subsisting, perceptive, all-noble, sole god, all-authoritative, expediter, delayer, first, perceptible, imperceptible, exalted, merciful, retaliator, pardoner, benign, sovereign, majestic, honorable, just, gatherer of creation, self-sufficient, distressor, bestower of sufficiency, preventer, bestower of benefits, prime light, provider of guidance, unique, ever-surviving, eternal inheritor, guide to path of rectitude, extensively enduring

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text only the Muslim high god, Allah.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Notes: The text only the Muslim high god, Allah.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– I don't know

Notes: This could be possible in the syncretized Islamic context of the precolonial East African coast.

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: None

Does the text guide divination practices?

– I don't know

Notes: The text could have been used to guide divinatory practices in the pre-colonial East African coast

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– I don't know

Notes: The dedicatory inscription says, "This is what has ordered the high and very great Shaikh es-Saiyid Abu 'Imran Musa, son of el Hasan, son of Muhammad . . .—may Allah grant him long life and destroy his enemies—about building this mosque on a Sunday of the month Dhu-lqa'da in the year five hundred (A.D. 1107)." This and the Quranic excerpts that are part of the inscription could be seen as a sign of supernatural monitoring.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: Not according to this text, but there are other texts that mention divine punishment in Islam.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– I don't know

Notes: The reward seems to be due to the construction of the mosque, but the phrasing of the inscription is ambiguous on this account. It says, "May Allah grant him..."

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– I don't know

Notes: The mention of reward in the inscription could be done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

Notes: The inscription specifically asks Allah to bless the person who commissioned the mosque.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– I don't know

Notes: The text asks or wishes Allah to bless the builder of the mosque, presumably as a reward for doing so.

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

Notes: The inscription requests/wishes Allah to grant the builder of the mosque long life and to destroy his enemies.

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

Notes: The inscription requests/wishes Allah to grant the builder of the mosque long life and to destroy his enemies.

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

Notes: The inscription requests/wishes Allah to grant the builder of the mosque long life and to destroy his enemies.

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– No

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

Notes: The inscription requests/wishes Allah to grant the builder of the mosque long life and to destroy his enemies.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The inscription requests/wishes Allah to grant the builder of the mosque long life and to destroy his enemies.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: But Messianic beliefs are present in other texts of Islam.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: But eschatology is present in other texts.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Notes: The text mentions the construction of a mosque, but the upkeep of mosques have been mentioned elsewhere in Islamic tradition.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A state

Notes: The community that built the mosque would have likely been associated with a state or large organized community through ties of trade and exchange.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A state

Notes: The production of the inscription was likely commissioned by a person who was a wealthy merchant and/or who had the resources to construct the mosque on Zanzibar. Specialist craftspersons were likely brought to the site to carve/incise the inscription.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A state

Notes: The text has not been destroyed. It has been preserved for over 900 years.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual/religious welfare.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Madrassas and other religious schools and non-religious schools would have existed to teach people to read the text.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Notes: Although not mentioned by the text, Madrasahs and other religious schools and non-religious schools would have existed to teach people to read the text.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education was generally limited to men in precolonial Muslim societies, although there were significant exceptions.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Notes: But the construction of the mosque itself could be considered public works.

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Notes: But the text does ask/wish Allah to destroy the enemies of the person who built the mosque.

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Kizimkazi Dimbani Mosque Inscription, Flury, S. "The Kufic Inscription of Kizimkazi Mosque, Zanzibar, AD 1107", 1922.